

EFFECT OF CONCRETE COVER ON BOND OF GFRP BARS IN ULTRA-HIGH-PERFORMANCE FIBER-REINFORCED CONCRETE (UHPFRC)

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ABSTRACT

This study aims at establishing the development length of sand-coated GFRP bars embedded into UHPFRC with a focus on the effect of concrete cover on bond strength. The study uses notched beam specimens tested in flexure where the bars are under realistic tensile stress as opposed to pull-out tests. The embedment length of the bars was varied in different beams to establish a correlation with the maximum tension force attained, thereby calculating the minimum embedment length required to enable the full tensile capacity of the bar, namely the development length. Concrete mixes containing 2% steel fibers were used for all specimens in the study. It was found that ACI440.11-22 code equation grossly overestimates GFRP bar development length in UHPFRC by a factor of 2.6-2.9. The Michaud et al. (2021) equation provided a much better prediction but was unable to account for varying concrete covers. As such, it overestimated development length by a factor of 1.3 for the thickest cover used in this study.

KEYWORDS

GFRP; UHPFRC; Development length; Sand-coated; Embedment length; Bar diameter; Concrete cover;

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars have proven to be an adequate alternative to steel rebar for tensile reinforcement in structural concrete members exposed to corrosive environments due to their excellent durability and high tensile strength (Benmokrane, 1996; Benmokrane et al., 1995). While the American Concrete Institute ACI Code-440.11-22 has been developed for the design of conventional normal strength concrete reinforced with GFRP bars, there are currently no design guides available for the use of this reinforcement within ultra-high-performance fiber-reinforced concrete (UHPFRC).

Michaud et al. (2021) specifically investigated the development length of sand-coated GFRP bars embedded in UHPFRC reinforced with steel or PVA fibers of varying contents, with only one small concrete cover and one standard bar diameter. From this study, it was found that using Eq. 1 below in ACI440.11-22 to estimate the development length of the 17 mm GFRP bar diameter (d_b) embedded in UHPFRC with small cover ($1.0d_b$) yields a substantial overestimation. As such, Michaud et al. (2021) developed an alternative Eq. 2 based on the limited data, which does not account for the effects of diameter and concrete cover.

$$l_d = \frac{\frac{f_{fr}}{0.083\sqrt{f'_c}} - 340}{13.6 + \frac{c}{d_b}} d_b \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\frac{l_d}{d_b} = \frac{1538}{\sqrt{f'_c}} - 113 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

This study aims to expand upon Eq. 2, by investigating the relationship of concrete cover on the development length of GFRP bars embedded in UHPFRC with 2% steel fibers.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

To date the test matrix included fabrication of 18 UHPFRC beams with a 2% steel fiber content. Each beam was reinforced in tension with a sand-coated GFRP #5 bar of varying embedment length and concrete cover. The following sections outline the specimen parameters, materials, fabrication process, and test setup.

Specimen Parameters

Each beam was cast in two halves, separated by an 18 mm gap, such that the UHPFRC was non continuous through the length of the beam. The single GFRP #5 bar was embedded equally into each half of the beam. Debonding of the GFRP bar at beam ends was varied between beams to achieve the desired embedment lengths, while midspan debonding was consistent across all specimens at 50 mm from either side of midspan. End and midspan debonding was achieved through the use of polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pipe and can be seen in Figure 1(a).

GFRP #5 bars were embedded at lengths of 4, 9, and 14 times the bar diameter, with clear concrete covers of 17.0, 23.0, or 42.0 mm. Two repetitions of each unique beam were fabricated and tested. All beams had identical cross sections of 150 x 180 mm. Beam lengths varied based on the embedment required.

Every beam was fabricated with a 64 x 44 mm notch at the top of midspan. This notch was used as a cavity for a steel roller which acted as a distinct transfer point for the compression force in the beam during flexural testing at any load level. The distinct transfer point then allowed for an accurate calculation of the moment arm between the compression force and tension force in the GFRP bar, thereby enabling accurate calculation of the tension force knowing the maximum moment from external loading of the beam.

Each beam half was additionally reinforced longitudinally by two 10M steel bars that were noncontinuous through midspan. Two small diameter (3 mm) steel stirrups were used to fasten a vertical layer of small diameter (3 mm) steel mesh spaced at 50 mm to each steel bar, for the purpose of shear reinforcement. These ‘cages’ were developed such that their clear cover from all sides of their respective beam was 15 mm. A sample of these cages can be seen in Figure 1(b).

a) Formwork
b) Steel reinforcing cage
Figure 1: Sample of formwork and steel reinforcing cage

Materials

UHPFRC

A total of 14 different mixes is required to pour all planned 42 test specimens. Each mix contained a fiber content of 2% steel. The steel fibers that were used were 13 mm long, with a diameter of 0.2 mm and tensile strength of 2850 MPa. 2% steel fiber content is one of the most common mix parameters in industry according to the manufacturer. Cylinders measuring approximately 75 mm x 150 mm were poured from the mixes and tested after 28 days, within 48 hours of their associated specimen tests. The average compressive strength and standard deviation of the mixes was 129 MPa and 14.4 MPa respectively. The modulus of rupture according to Russell and Graybeal (2013) is $0.55\sqrt{f'_c} = 6.25$ MPa.

GFRP Rebar

Grade III sand-coated GFRP #5 bars consisting of boron-free glass fibers in vinyl ester resin were used in this study. The bars had a nominal guaranteed tensile strength of 1100 MPa and minimum modulus of elasticity of 60 GPa. Table 1 outlines the additional specifications of the bars.

Table 1: V-Rod GFRP rebar specifications

Bar Size	Bar diameter	CS Area <i>avg, std dev</i>	Tensile strength <i>avg, std dev</i>	Elastic modulus <i>avg, std dev</i>	Shear strength <i>avg, std dev</i>
15M (#5)	17.3 mm	234, 0.6 mm	1402, 26.2 MPa	62.2, 0.45 GPa	249, 13.7 MPa

Fabrication Process

The UHPFRC materials were mixed in a high shear mixer at the Queen's University structures lab in Ellis Hall, following the mixing process provided by the supplier. After mixing, the UHPFRC was poured into the wooden formwork for the beams, and plastic tubes for the cylinders. The exposed surface of the beams was covered with water-soaked burlap to continually apply moisture to the beams, and a plastic sheet to slow down the evaporation of the water. The burlap was re-soaked every other day for seven days after pouring, as per the manufacturer's instruction. The beams were left to cure in a temperature-controlled environment at 23 ± 3 °C.

Test Setup

The test setup used in this study was based on the RILEM RC5 bond test for reinforcement steel, which has been superseded by the British Standard EN 10080:2005 – Annex D (British Standards, 2005) and can be seen in Figure 2(a). Each beam specimen was non-continuous at midspan, with the exception of a single GFRP bar. The beam was loaded in four-point bending on the RIEHLE test machine, at a rate of 0.5 mm/min. The exact distance between the centre of the steel roller on the top compression side and the centre of the GFRP bar on the bottom tension side was measured and recorded for each specimen. This distance was used to accurately determine the tensile force in the GFRP bar at failure as indicated earlier.

Four linear potentiometers (LPs) were used to measure displacements. LP1 was positioned at the precise depth of the GFRP bar centre, to measure the elongation and slip of the bar at midspan, LP2 measured the vertical displacement of the beam 20 mm offset from midspan, and LPs 3 and 4 measured the slip of the bar at the ends of the beam relative to the end face of the concrete beam. The LP locations can be seen in Figures 2(b) and 2(c).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Table 2 outlines the design parameters of each beam, as well as the key testing results. Figure 3 displays load vs deflection, maximum end slip and midspan gap opening for beams with the smallest span, and Figure 4 displays similar plots for beams with the middle-sized span. Maximum end slip plots use either LP3 or LP4 based on whichever recorded higher values. It should be noted that Figures 3 and 4 only display the results of the specimen that achieved the highest peak load of each beam pair.

Figure 2: General test setup and LP locations

Table 2: Test matrix and results

Specimen ID	f'_c (MPa)	Bar diameter (mm)	Cover (mm)	Embedment length (mm)	Maximum bar stress (MPa)	Average bond strength (MPa)	Failure mode
5-1	138.8	17.3	25	74.1	284.1	16.5	S
5-2	132.9	17.3	26	74.1	304.2	17.7	S
6-1	138.8	17.3	31	74.1	310.2	18.0	S
6-2	132.9	17.3	30	74.1	335.6	19.5	S
7-1	145.8	17.3	50	74.1	352.6	20.5	P
7-2	118.0	17.3	52	74.1	365.6	21.2	P
12-1	124.3	17.3	25	155.4	550.4	15.2	S
12-2	141.8	17.3	25	155.4	582.8	16.1	S
13-1	124.3	17.3	25	241.7	713.4	12.7	S
13-2	128.1	17.3	25	241.7	773.4	13.8	S
14-1	124.3	17.3	31	155.4	590.9	16.4	S
14-2	128.1	17.3	31	155.4	624.5	17.3	S
15-1	128.6	17.3	30	241.7	634.7	11.3	S
15-2	117.9	17.3	31	241.7	845.5	15.1	S
16-1	128.6	17.3	47	155.4	695.0	19.3	S
16-2	119.5	17.3	51	155.4	744.6	20.6	S
17-1	119.5	17.3	51	241.7	858.5	15.3	S
17-2	127.6	17.3	50	241.7	896.0	16.0	S

Figure 3: Load vs. deflection, end slip, and midspan gap opening slip for small span beams

Figure 4: Load vs. deflection, end slip, and midspan gap opening for medium span beams

Test Results and Analysis

In this study, every specimen failed in bond; most commonly splitting type failure (“S” in Table 2), with only one specimen pair 7 failing in pullout (“P” in Table 2) which are the specimens with the largest cover of 50 mm combined with minimum embedment length of 74 mm. This pair did not show any signs of surface cracking, signifying the different pullout failure mode. Pullout failure occurs when the GFRP bar experiences complete debonding from the surrounding concrete and slips out of place.

All beams that experienced splitting failure showed longitudinal cracking, with the length and width of the cracks varying depending on the specimen. Beam pair 15 stands out relative to other beams showing long and wide cracks that are reflected in their load-deflection responses with large load drops. This is also due to these specimens having relatively large embedment lengths, as cracking occurs along the entire bonded region of the GFRP bar. This cracking pattern has been seen in other studies exploring GFRP bars embedded in UHPFRC with PVA fibers, as well as steel bars embedded in UHPFRC (Michaud et al., 2021; Dagenais and Massicotte, 2015; Yuan and Graybeal, 2015).

Since splitting bond failure governed, the response close to failure was primarily governed by the tensile behaviour of UHPFRC. This explains the slight load plateau before failure of the beams, as this response is common in UHPFRC when cracking begins to occur (Graybeal and Baby, 2013). All specimens showed very insignificant slip (<1 mm) at beam ends prior to the peak load, and then a significant increase in slip at beam ends simultaneous to the load drop that was experienced during failure. Load drop was substantial in many cases, caused by a sudden longitudinal splitting crack through the full depth of the cover and allowing the GFRP bar to slip, ultimately relieving stress in the bar.

The maximum longitudinal tensile stress in the GFRP bar (f_s) embedded in each specimen was calculated using the following equation:

$$f_s = \frac{Pa}{2yA_b} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where P is the peak load achieved by the specimen, and A_b is the cross-sectional area of the GFRP bar. Figure 2 illustrates a as the shear span between the support and the point load, and y as the vertical distance between the tension force (middle of GFRP bar) and the compression force (middle of steel roller). The (f_s) for each specimen can be found in Table 2. Figures 5 and 6 show the relationships of embedment length to bar diameter (L_e/d_b) ratio for different clear covers (C_c), and cover to bar diameter (C/d_b) ratio for different (L_e/d_b) ratios, plotted respectively with (f_s). The plots clearly show that both design parameters: cover and embedment length, have positive relationships with (f_s) developed in the GFRP bar.

Figure 5 shows that for the largest clear cover of 42 mm the trend suggests a development length to diameter (L_d/d_b) ratio of 17.5 while for the smaller clear covers of 17 mm and 23 mm, the (L_d/d_b) ratio is approximately 21 for both. Figure 6 demonstrates how increasing the cover effectively implies a vertical upwards shift in the plots in Figure 5 which means a reduction in development length.

Assessment of Existing Design Equations

ACI Code-440.11-22 Eq. 1 for development length has been applied to the experimental case using an average concrete compressive strength of 129 MPa to predict the (L_d/d_b) ratio for the #5 (17.3 mm) GFRP bar for the three concrete covers. The predicted (L_d/d_b) ratio for the C_c values of 17, 23 and 42 mm are 55.0, 53.7, 50.1, respectively. This clearly overestimated (L_d/d_b) by 2.6 to 2.9 times.

Michaud et al. (2021) developed alternative equation (Eq. 2) for GFRP bars in UHPFRC but because their study did not vary the concrete cover, the equation in turn does not account for it. Applying Eq. 2 to the current experimental study for GFRP bar #5 results in a single (L_d/d_b) ratio of 22.8. Equation 2 was

developed based on a single bar diameter and a small cover of $1.0d_b$. As such, the 22.8 ratio obtained here is very close to the ratio of 21 measured experimentally in this study for the clear cover of 17 mm. This, however, underscores the importance of updating and extending Eq. 2 to account for different concrete covers and also calibrate it for different bar diameters. The experimental program is currently being expanded for two additional bar diameters with different concrete covers.

Figure 5: Maximum longitudinal tensile bar stress vs. embedment length to bar diameter ratio

Figure 6: Maximum longitudinal tensile bar stress vs. cover to bar diameter ratio

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented one of three phases of a comprehensive experimental bond study of sand-coated GFRP bars embedded in UHPFRC. This phase focused on one bar size (#5) with a 17.3 mm diameter and varying the clear concrete cover from 17 to 42 mm. A series of 18 split beam tests were conducted where the embedment length was varied from 74 mm to 242 mm. The following preliminary conclusions are drawn:

1. All beams failed by bond splitting failure where a longitudinal crack developed within the cover and the bar slipped, except for 2 (out of 18 beams) with the largest cover and shortest embedment length which failed by pullout without cracking.
2. Based on the single bar diameter tested (17.3 mm) it was found that the development length-to-diameter (L_d/d_b) ratio is 17.5 for the largest clear cover of 42 mm and 21 for the smaller clear covers of 17 mm and 23 mm.
3. ACI Code-440.11-22 code equation grossly overestimates the (L_d/d_b) ratio of GFRP bars in UHPFRC by factors of 2.6 to 2.9.
4. The Michaud et al. (2021) equation for GFRP bars in UHPFRC predicted a (L_d/d_b) ratio of 22.8 which is much closer than the ACI code equation, however, it is a single value for all covers as the equation does not account for concrete cover. As such, it overestimated the (L_d/d_b) ratio for the largest clear cover of 42 mm by a factor of 1.3.
5. The remaining experimental work will vary by diameter and concrete cover for each diameter and will expand the Michaud et al. (2021) equation to account for concrete cover and calibrate an expression for different diameters.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.